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AGREEMENT INGV-DPC 2012-2021
VOLCANOLOGICAL PROGRAMME 2012-2015

**PROJECT V3 – MULTI-DISCIPLINARY ANALYSIS OF THE RELATIONSHIPS
BETWEEN TECTONIC STRUCTURES AND VOLCANIC ACTIVITY
(ETNA, VULCANO-LIPARI SYSTEM)**

Final Report

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Web site on the DPC-INGV Volcanological projects

<https://sites.google.com/a/ingv.it/volcpro2014/>

Immagine di frontespizio

Lipari, Vulcano, e l'Etna sullo sfondo, in una immagine 3D da satellite ricostruita da sensori termici, radiometrici e radar
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Normazione ortoeditoriale, Revisione testi e Impaginazione

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Section 2

Scientific Reports of Research Units (RU 4)

Task 2 – WP 5

Dynamics and kinematics of the eastern flank from seismological and ground deformation analyses (Etna)

Participants: INOGS-TS

Angela Saraò, Luca Moratto

Other institutions

INGV-CT Ornella Cocina, Luciano Scarfi

Sp2 – Earthquake features through the seismic moment tensor (resp. A. Saraò)

We computed the seismic moment tensor of 50 earthquakes ($3.4 \leq M_L \leq 4.8$) occurred in the period 2005-2013 (Fig. 5) and recorded by the broad-band network of INGV-CT. For our analysis we employed the method developed by Dreger (e.g. Minson and Dreger, 2008), widely adopted in many seismological observatories, with the aim to tune and test this algorithm for computation in near real-time in the Etna area.

The comparison of the best moment tensors with fault plane solutions calculated by first arrival polarities (Scarfi et al., 2013) shows an excellent agreement of solutions (Fig. 6).

Figure 5. Epicentral distribution and moment tensor of the earthquakes (yellow circles) extracted from the INGV-CT web catalogue (Gruppo Analisi Dati Sismici, 2014).

Figure 6. Comparison of moment tensor (black) with fault plane solutions computed by first polarities (red), published in the INGV-CT web catalogue (Scarfi et al. 2013).

Looking at the percentages of moment tensor component (Fig. 7), we observe an interesting pattern of distribution of the double couple (DC) linked to shear dislocations, and non-DC (CLVD+ISO), possibly related to lenticular crack activation accompanied by possible presence of fluids (CLVD), and volume changes due to implosion or explosion (ISO). In Tab. 6 the solutions obtained by our analysis are listed (Saraò et al, 2014a, 2014b).

We observe that, if we consider the overall dataset (Fig. 7a), the DC component is dominating on the other components but we notice a different trend when splitting the plot in different areas of the volcano; in

the NE area (Fig. 7b), we have a predominance of non-DCs that can be related to the fluids circulation observed also by independent geophysical and geochemical measurements (Siniscalchi et al., 2010). In the NW area (Fig. 7c), the high DC components are associated with deep earthquakes (up to 30 km b.s.l.) and may be due to the activation of the regional tectonic structures related to the Apenninic-Maghrebian Chain compressive regime (Alparone et al., 2010). In the central area (Fig. 7d), the high DCs of the events belonging to the seismic swarm accompanying the 2008 eruption might be related with the formation of the dry eruptive field during the eruption (Aloisi et al., 2009).

Figure 7. Boxplots with the percentage of moment tensor component (DC, CLVD and ISO) for: a) the whole dataset; b) data of the NE area; c) data of NW sector; d) data of central area (summit) of the volcano. On each box, the central mark (red) is the median, the edges of the box are the 25th and 75th percentiles, the whiskers extend to the most extreme data points not considered outliers.

To obtain a relation M_w vs. M_L , the M_w calculated during this study (red stars in Fig. 8) have been integrated with the M_w obtained by Saraò et al. (2010) through the moment tensor for a selection of earthquakes ($2.0 < M_d < 3.8$), occurred during the early hours of a seismic swarm forerunning the 2001 eruption (blue stars in Fig. 8). For the 2001 data, only the M_d was available, therefore we retrieved the M_L through the empirical relation $M_L - M_d$ by Tuvè et al. (2015). The final data set has been investigated through the generalized orthogonal regression (Fig. 8, black line and black equation). The error associated to the M_w is ± 0.2 . The error associated to the M_L is ± 0.3 .

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Figure 8. Relation M_L vs. M_w obtained in this study.

N	Date	Time	LAT	LONG	MI	Dep	Q	Str1	Dip1	Rak1	Str2	Dip2	Rak2	DC	CLVD	ISO	Mw	M_{ge21}
1	2005/07/10	13:38:51	37.852	14.991	3.4	29	2	189	79	-36	287	54	-167	38	39	23	3.4	1.34
2	2005/08/14	21:56:48	37.815	15.104	3.5	2	3	20	87	144	112	54	4	38	13	49	3.7	3.40
3	2005/10/30	06:06:50	37.652	15.058	3.7	9	3	47	74	23	310	68	162	14	53	33	3.8	6.22
4	2005/10/31	00:02:41	37.66	15.053	3.8	4	3	64	63	46	309	50	144	79	15	6	3.8	6.03
5	2006/01/08	16:09:24	37.683	14.97	3.7	12	3	178	87	-142	86	53	-4	75	12	13	3.8	6.34
6	2006/03/02	20:35:38	37.794	14.916	3.4	20	2	195	78	36	96	55	166	24	35	41	3.2	7.48
7	2006/05/20	07:05:56	37.667	14.945	3.8	10	3	87	68	27	346	65	156	27	26	47	3.7	4.21
8	2006/06/19	20:55:34	37.844	14.879	4.0	24	3	102	64	-145	355	59	-31	71	24	5	3.9	8.48
9	2006/06/20	13:16:35	37.839	14.886	3.4	24	1	127	63	-122	2	41	-44	49	8	44	3.3	0.99
10	2006/12/19	14:58:05	37.775	14.862	4.5	26	3	102	89	-174	12	84	-1	50	37	13	4	11.5
11	2006/12/20	01:46:23	37.778	14.908	3.4	24	2	209	71	21	112	70	159	48	19	32	3.7	3.95
12	2008/04/09	04:14:36	37.727	15.126	3.5	8	4	108	81	34	12	57	169	59	25	16	3.8	6.49
13	2008/05/01	21:05:47	37.802	15.041	3.5	1	3	80	85	-29	173	61	-174	29	33	38	3.7	3.82
14	2008/05/13	09:23:04	37.776	14.993	3.6	6	3	232	78	-155	136	66	-13	43	42	16	3.7	4.01
15	2008/05/13	09:28:05	37.764	15.007	3.8	2	3	193	64	-39	303	56	-147	58	25	17	3.8	5.10
16	2008/05/13	09:56:38	37.761	15.021	3.6	5	3	81	85	-59	180	31	-170	73	16	11	3.7	3.37
17	2008/05/13	10:07:48	37.771	15.005	3.9	2	3	142	60	-141	30	57	-36	84	14	2	3.7	4.61
18	2008/05/13	11:03:32	37.768	15.001	3.7	2	3	273	88	159	4	69	2	14	35	50	3.5	1.81
19	2008/05/13	11:52:38	37.766	14.999	3.6	2	3	248	54	-84	58	36	-98	22	38	40	3.5	1.69
20	2008/05/13	12:13:42	37.765	15.009	3.8	1	3	164	62	109	307	33	58	12	85	3	3.9	7.03
21	2008/05/13	13:26:49	37.771	15.003	3.7	2	2	234	77	32	136	59	164	70	24	7	3.7	4.38
22	2008/05/13	21:28:27	37.809	15.058	3.4	1	3	179	88	-174	89	84	-2	15	33	52	3.6	2.75
23	2008/12/16	02:30:14	37.664	14.952	4.0	8	3	162	70	-157	64	68	-22	91	5	4	3.7	3.35
24	2009/03/14	09:26:51	37.73	15.096	3.5	6	3	36	90	-176	306	86	0	45	49	6	3.5	2.18
25	2009/05/13	14:13:46	37.712	15.165	3.6	2	3	220	82	-17	312	73	-172	40	10	51	3.9	8.26
26	2009/07/23	00:10:42	37.589	14.763	3.7	22	2	263	80	-13	355	78	-170	17	62	21	3.6	3.26
27	2009/08/25	16:58:02	37.812	15.097	3.6	2	3	274	80	-29	10	62	-168	7	72	21	3.6	2.43
28	2009/12/19	05:36:00	37.79	14.913	4.4	22	3	205	57	64	66	41	123	47	18	35	4.5	73.9
29	2009/12/19	07:42:25	37.774	14.881	3.7	22	3	203	64	69	63	33	126	43	49	8	3.9	8.1
30	2009/12/19	08:01:10	37.769	14.905	3.6	20	2	239	56	122	11	45	52	55	1	44	3.8	6.61
31	2009/12/19	08:24:57	37.776	14.911	3.8	19	3	223	63	95	31	27	80	57	15	28	4.1	14.3
32	2009/12/19	09:01:14	37.794	14.869	4.8	28	2	217	65	64	87	35	134	87	6	6	4.7	132
33	2009/12/19	12:35:40	37.781	14.915	3.5	20	3	15	88	-55	108	35	-177	30	26	45	3.6	3.33
34	2009/12/19	12:43:10	37.792	14.916	3.8	24	3	269	84	156	1	66	6	58	24	18	3.9	7.51
35	2009/12/19	18:08:33	37.805	14.886	3.5	20	2	186	59	-139	71	55	-38	71	3	26	3.5	1.92
36	2009/12/23	14:24:42	37.795	14.91	3.7	18	2	255	58	106	47	35	67	24	40	36	3.7	3.36
37	2010/04/02	20:04:00	37.806	15.078	4.3	3	3	8	79	163	101	73	12	59	9	32	4.3	26.7
38	2010/04/02	20:21:55	37.807	15.106	3.5	2	2	99	81	13	7	77	171	23	69	9	3.4	1.35
39	2011/05/06	15:12:35	37.804	14.943	4	14	4	274	72	129	24	42	27	44	52	4	4	11.7
40	2011/05/06	15:15:23	37.798	14.949	3.4	23	1	269	83	164	1	74	7	81	14	5	3.4	1.56
41	2011/05/06	15:18:30	37.803	14.914	3.4	20	1	282	89	166	13	76	1	14	6	80	3.4	1.55
42	2011/05/06	19:28:49	37.797	14.933	3.5	20	2	352	76	17	258	74	166	87	8	4	3.5	2.05
43	2011/05/11	01:45:35	37.804	14.933	3.5	20	1	257	81	152	352	63	10	49	11	41	3.8	5.11
44	2011/05/11	02:17:08	37.801	14.94	3.4	20	1	70	85	-173	340	83	-5	11	18	71	3.8	5.57
45	2011/09/09	22:23:44	37.827	14.793	4	26	3	239	84	102	355	14	27	55	43	2	3.9	6.95

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46	2012/01/01	04:17:02	37.879	14.865	3.5	32	1	107	83	163	199	73	7	74	23	4	3.8	5.03
47	2012/11/22	09:10:41	37.791	14.94	4.2	12	4	262	71	159	359	71	20	95	5	0	3.9	7.02
48	2012/11/22	11:25:51	37.799	14.936	4.3	20	3	253	70	125	10	39	33	64	6	29	4.2	19.8
49	2012/11/22	11:28:55	37.792	14.947	3.9	12	4	262	76	155	358	66	16	82	10	8	3.8	6.50
50	2013/05/23	13:04:48	37.696	15.089	3.4	4	1	142	89	18	52	72	179	32	50	18	3.4	1.34

Table 6. Earthquakes investigated in this study by moment tensor. For each event are reported: progressive number (N), date (Date), time (Time UTC), Latitude N (Lat.), Longitude E (Long.) in degrees, M_L, depth in km (De), quality of the inversion (Q=4, excellent, Q=0 poor), strike (Str), dip (Dip), rake (Rak) for both planes in degrees, double couple (DC), CLVD, isotropic component (ISO) percentage, M_w and seismic moment (M₀) in 10e+21 dynecm.

Deliverables

- WP 1.Sp1 Revision of the average time of occurrence of earthquakes along the Timpe faults: **100%**.
 WP 3.Sp1 Maps including site and topographic effects (30, 20, 10 and 5 yrs): **90%**.
 WP 5.Sp2 Earthquake features through the seismic moment tensor: **100%**.

Problems and difficulties

The problems and difficulties are due to the compression of a 3-years activity in 2 annual phases only. This fact implies that some of the analyses, mainly related to Task 1-Wp 3, have been performed at the very last minute, and do not have right now an adequate level of cross-checking and controls.

Key publications

- Azzaro R., D'Amico S., Pace B., Peruzza L. (2015). *Is a geometric-kinematic approach valid for estimating the expected seismicity rates in volcano-tectonic areas? Ideas and results from seismogenic sources at Mt. Etna (Italy)*. INQUA Focus Group on Paleoseismology and Active Tectonics 6th International INQUA Meeting on Paleoseismology, Active Tectonics and Archaeoseismology, 19-24 April 2015, Pescina, Fucino Basin, Italy, 3 pp.
- Azzaro R., D'Amico S., Pace B., Peruzza L. (2014). *Estimating the expected seismicity rates of volcano-tectonic earthquakes at Mt. Etna (Italy) by a geometric-kinematic approach*. Extended abstract presented at the 33° Convegno Nazionale GNGTS, Bologna (Italy), November 25-27, 2014.
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- Saraò A., Cocina O., Scarfi L. (2014b). *Estimates of complete moment tensor of seismicity occurred at Mt. Etna in the period 2005-2013*. Abstract presented at Conferenza A. Rittmann, Nicolosi (Catania) 29-31 Oct. 2014, Italy. Miscellanea INGV, vol. 25, 160-161. ISSN 2039-6651.

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- Scarfi L., Messina A., Cassisi C., (2013). *Sicily and Southern Calabria focal mechanism database: a valuable tool for the local and regional stress field determination*. Annals of Geophysics, 56, 1, D0109; doi:10.4401/ag-6109. <http://sismoweb.ct.ingv.it/focal/>
- Siniscalchi A., Tripaldi S., Neri M., Giammanco S., Piscitelli S., Balasco M., Behncke B., Magri C., Naudet V., Rizzo E., (2010). *Insights into fluid circulation across the Pernicana Fault (Mt. Etna, Italy) and implications for flank instability*. J. Volcanol. Geotherm. Res. 193, 137-142, doi: 10.1016/j.jvolgeores.2010.03.013
- Tuvè T., D'Amico S. and Giampiccolo E. (2015). *A new Local vs. Duration magnitude relationship for the Mt. Etna seismic catalogue*. Annals of Geophysics, accepted.